

Race and gender representation and topical alignment in South African scholarly publications

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Abstract

Decades after apartheid, South Africa grapples with persistent racial and gender inequalities, notably in labor and education. This study employs the South Africa Knowledgebase (SAK) to analyze racial and gender disparities among South African researchers, uncovering insights into academic representation, collaboration patterns, and thematic distributions. Our results reveal significant underrepresentation of Black and Coloured authors, particularly women, in South African research, relative to national population proportions. Gendered patterns emerge, with women's peak participation occurring earlier in their careers, suggesting targeted policies to sustain their involvement. Field and topic distributions reflect intersectional identities, impacting knowledge production and reinforcing societal inequalities. Active science policies are imperative to address underrepresentation and its detrimental effects on innovation and societal equity. Understanding the root causes demands comprehensive examination across educational and career pathways.

Keywords:

Inequalities, intersectionality, race & gender, South Africa

1. Introduction

Systemic racism has long-lasting pervasive consequences. Three decades after the end of apartheid, the cumulative nature of inequalities continues to reproduce racial segregation in contemporary South Africa. Despite policy efforts, racial segregation remains widespread across the labor market in post-apartheid South Africa. More than 90% of people who participated in job creation programs are Black Africans (Statistics South Africa, 2023); however, this group remains the most underprivileged. Low-skilled positions account for a large portion of the jobs for Black African (33.4%) and Colored (30.8%) workers, at rates that are times higher than for White workers (3.2%). There are also divides by gender: 34% of women have low-skilled jobs, compared to 24.7% of men (Statistics South Africa, 2023). Black African and Coloured workers are also more likely to work in the informal sector¹, agriculture, and especially in private households than White workers. As a consequence, White workers are twice as likely to have medical aid coverage (Statistics South Africa, 2023). From an intersectional lens, Black and Coloured women are overrepresented in low-paying jobs, while White and Indian/Asian women tend to fill higher-paying professional positions (Gradín, 2021).

Prior research also indicates that White students have consistently received more, and higher quality education compared to Black students (McKeever, 2017). This is further compounded by the challenges Black students face in affording academic fees, leading to higher dropout rates (Higham, 2012). Despite several policies seeking to address racial inequities in the post-apartheid era, persistent educational and economic inequalities remain (Badat & Sayed, 2014).

At the post-secondary level, research outputs are heavily concentrated among eight universities — the University of Cape Town, the University of Witwatersrand, the University of Stellenbosch, the University of Pretoria, the University of KwaZulu-Natal, the University of South Africa, and the University of Western Cape — which together published more than 70% of scholarly articles between 1966 to 2014 (Potgieter et al., 2016). Since the 1970s, collaborative efforts have become increasingly prevalent among South African researchers (Potgieter et al., 2016), with almost half of publications originating from international collaborations in the 2012-2021 period, with a large presence of European countries and the United States, rather than neighboring countries (Heleta & Jithoo, 2023). Differences in author productivity generate unequal career trajectories, particularly given the role that gender plays in faculty promotion to more senior positions (Shober, 2014). Language barriers for non-English native speakers and inadequate mentoring have also posed significant challenges for young researchers (Rapanyane, 2021).

Within this context, this manuscript aims to understand the racial and gender disparities among researchers in South African universities. Using the South Africa Knowledgebase (SAK) of institutionally-reported publications, and author self-identified race, gender, and age, we

¹ Informal sector comprises individuals in small establishments and unregistered businesses (Statistics South Africa, 2023).

mapped South African researchers and the topic of their research articles. Our goals for this project were three-fold: to understand 1) how race and gender identities are represented among South African-based authors by varying academic ages, 2) the relationship between author identity and international collaboration, and 3) how author identities are distributed across fields and topics.

2. Data and Methods

This article utilizes bibliographic and sociodemographic data from the SA Knowledgebase (SAK), hosted at the Centre for Research on Evaluation, Science and Technology (CREST) at Stellenbosch University. It is based on the institutionally-reported publications that appeared in journals accredited by South Africa's Department of Higher Education and Training (DHET) from authors housed in South African universities (Tijssen et al., 2006), along with self-declared sociodemographic data (i.e., race, gender, age). As of November 2022, the SAK contained information for 95,199 unique authors and 247,068 scholarly papers published between 2005 and 2020. This database is unique for intersectional studies, as it contains, for a large percentage of South African authors, self-declared race, gender, biological age at the time of publication, and country of birth. This represents a step forward from previous studies on gender and race, which estimated identities based on authors' first and/or last names (and race (Kozlowski et al., 2022; Larivière et al., 2013). A total of 26 South African universities reported their publications, with varying numbers of articles per institution, with a high concentration among the 8 top universities from the country, as mentioned above.

In terms of coverage of various socio-demographic information, 73% of authors reported their gender, 66% their race, and 48% their age². Therefore, the analysis in this article that corresponds to each of these variables is limited to those subsets of the population. We observed, however, strong correlations among the missing socio-demographic variables in the data. For instance, 66% of authors reported both their race and gender, and the 48% of authors who reported their age also provided information on both race and gender. Of the 95,199 authors, 69,131 self-identified as "Male" or "Female"³, and 26,067 did not report any gender. One author self-identified as "Not classified as Male or Female". Given that including this individual in the results would affect their anonymity, we restrict our analysis to a binary classification of gender. For the self-identification of race, 1,134 authors replied "Non-SA citizen", although 13,454 authors with a country of birth different from South Africa did report their race within one of the established categories. As race is a social construct deeply embedded within national contexts, we understand that migrant authors might not feel represented within the South African categorization. For example, 574 authors identified as "other" with regard to race. For this study, we retain the following SAK categories: Black, Coloured, Indian/Asian, and White, restricting our analyses to the 61,302 authors that identified as one of these categories.

² Since the time of data collection, SAK has greatly reduced the number of missing variables. Therefore, these analyses will be rerun on the newer dataset prior to the presentation at STI.

³ SAK uses "Female" or "Male" to report the gender of authors. As we consider that this terminology refers to biological sex rather than gender, we replace these terms with "Women" or "Men" in the rest of the manuscript.

As a benchmark, we use projections from the South African Census Bureau (Statistics South Africa, 2022). We use a consolidated version of the yearly projections of the Census that correspond to the period range of the SAK database. The information by the Census is presented in five-year age ranges (i.e., population between 0 and 5, 5 and 10, etc.). For comparability, we group the SAK authors into the same categories and focus our attention on authors aged 20 years and above. Under/overrepresentation with respect to the Census is computed as the ratio between the proportion of authors that correspond to a race, gender, and age group over the proportion of the Census population that corresponds to that demographic group, considering only the population over 20 years old. This is:

$$relative\ representation = \frac{\frac{N_{r,g,a}^{authors}}{N_{r,g,a}^{population}}}{\frac{N_{r,g,a}^{population}}{N_{r,g,a}^{population}}} - 1 = \frac{prop_{r,g,a}^{authors}}{prop_{r,g,a}^{population}}$$

where r is the racial group, g is the gender, and a is the age group. The use of this denominator is the most extreme assumption — that is, that each member of the population would have equal opportunity for scientific authorship. This is the baseline from which other measures of representation can be measured — e.g., racial composition in secondary education, composition of those who matriculate/graduate in tertiary education; those employed in the academic sector as researchers, professors, or lecturers.

The normalisation with respect to a given demographic characteristic means that the comparison is made to that group alone. For example, for the normalisation by age and race:

$$relative\ representation_{norm_{age\ \&\ race}}^{r,a} = \frac{\frac{N_g^{authors_{r,a}}}{N_{r,a}^{authors_{r,a}}}}{\frac{N_g^{population_{r,a}}}{N_{r,a}^{population_{r,a}}}} - 1 = \frac{prop_g^{authors_{r,a}}}{prop_g^{population_{r,a}}}$$

where the superindex r, a means that this calculation is performed for each race and age group separately.

Topics were defined using the BERTopic pipeline (Grootendorst, 2022), using unigrams from papers' titles and removing English stopwords on the word vectorizer. The Hdbscan model for clustering has a min cluster size of 20, which creates a model with 1,455 topics, and most outlier articles were resigned with BERTopic default strategy. We chose to exclusively utilize paper titles instead of titles and abstracts because in the SAK database, this enables us to utilize the entire database rather than only those entries that can be matched to WOS for abstract retrieval, which accounts for approximately 50% of entries. Furthermore, as Bertopic uses pre-trained embeddings as a starting point, it is a tool suited to train a meaningful representation of short strings such as titles.

3. Results

Representation

Figure 1A shows the relation between the proportion of authors of a given race, gender, and age group, compared with its proportion reported in the Census (excluding people under 20 years of age). Indian/Asian authors are three times more represented among authors than in the general population for their equivalent age sets, whereas White authors are five to six

times more prevalent as scientific authors than their share of the Census population. This overrepresentation is concomitant with an underrepresentation of Black and Colored authors.

Figure 1. Relative representation of authors from each race, gender, and age group with respect to the census. Figure A shows no normalization, while B normalizes the results by age, C by race and gender, and D by age and race.

We normalize this ratio by age (Figure 1B) to understand how the representation of a given race and gender at a given age group compares to the representation of the other demographic groups of that same age. The results present a very different evolution of representation: while White and Indian/Asian authors from both genders are overrepresented at the beginning of their careers (ages 20-24), women's overrepresentation declines with age, while men, and in particular White men, show a stable overrepresentation over time. Normalizing by race and gender (Figure 1C), shows how the representation of a given race and gender at a given age compares to the representation of this same identity at other ages. These results demonstrate a clear gendered pattern, while women's representation peaks between the ages of 25 and 35, that of men peak at an older age. We can also see that representation patterns for women are more stable across racial groups than those for men. Black men peak at a younger age, between 35 and 45, while White men's representation peaks between 55 and 65. While overrepresentation is heavily associated with race, the life cycle of authors is even more related with their gender. By comparing within each age and race (Figure 1D), we observe the gender divide within each racial group at each given age. For all racial groups, women are more represented at earlier career ages, and the pattern is reversed for older groups. This result might be related with the unequal effect of parenthood among women and men in academia (Morgan et al., 2021). Colored, Indian/Asian, and White authors find this reversion around their 40s, while for Black authors this occurs at a much younger age, around 25.

Relative representation shows how an identity group is over or under-represented in a field, with respect to the overall population of that identity group among all authors. For example, Black women represent 11.8% of the authors but only 8.5% of the authors in Humanities and Arts, and therefore are underrepresented by 28%. Figure 2A presents fields sorted by the relative representation of Black women. Black women are relatively more represented in Social Sciences and Health Sciences, and underrepresented in the Humanities, Arts, and Natural Sciences. The exact opposite distribution can be found for White men. Generally speaking, women are overrepresented in Health Sciences and underrepresented in Natural Sciences. Similarly, in Engineering, men from nearly all racial groups are overrepresented while women are underrepresented.

On the other hand, some fields show patterns of racial segregation. In Humanities and Arts for example, both White men and women are overrepresented by a larger margin than in any other field, and all other groups, except for Colored men, are underrepresented. Indian/Asian authors show the most skewed distributions, with high overrepresentation in Engineering for men and Health sciences for women.

Figure 2. Representation of race and gender within specific fields relative to their proportion of the total population (A). International collaborations by race and gender (B). Panel (C) shows the above or below expected value given the disciplinary distribution by demographic group. South African publications in WOS

International collaborations are also not homogeneously distributed. Figure 2B shows the proportion of international collaborations by race and gender. Black and Colored authors tend to have fewer international collaborations, while Indian/Asian and White authors tend to have more. Across racial groups, men tend to have more international collaborations than women, but while the difference is smaller for Black and Colored authors, it grows between White men and women, and it is particularly large in the case of Asian/Indian authors. As different fields have different collaboration patterns (Larivière et al., 2015), and we have seen that the

proportion of authors by race and gender across fields is not equal (Figure 2A), we compute the expected proportion of international collaborations of a race and gender identity given their distribution across fields and compare it with the observed distribution (Figure 2D). We can observe that both racial and gender inequalities are exacerbated in terms of international collaboration, with Black women collaborating 20% less than expected given their distribution across fields, and Asian/Indian men collaborating 15% more than expected. Black and Colored men and women and Indian/Asian women show values below expected, White women are almost at the expected values, and White men and Indian/Asian men are above expected values.

Research Topics

To analyze how race and gender identities are distributed within fields, we developed a semi-supervised BERT-based topic modelling (Grootendorst, 2022) of articles. Topics are then assigned to the field that corresponds to the majority of the articles that compose them. Figure 3 shows the proportion of articles that are authored by women (vertical axis) and each of the four racial groups (horizontal axis of each panel). For each racial group and for women, we selected the ten topics where the proportion of authors from each group was the highest and hand-labelled them based on their 10 most salient terms. The y-axis provides the feminization of a topic and the x-axis the racialization. Therefore, a topic in the top-right quadrant is both racialized and feminized, a topic in top-left quadrant is highly feminized but not disproportionately associated with the given race; and a topic in bottom-right quadrant is highly identified with that racial category, but not with women authors.

As observed in Figure 2, women are more present in Health-related publications. At the topic level we identify many health-related topics, specifically around care work with a high proportion of women authors. *Nursing* is a notable topic, which appears for both Health and Social Sciences, in addition to more granular topics such as *Nurses burnout* and *care for nurses*. *Midwives* also appear as a relevant topic for both Health and Social Sciences, the latter being particularly important for Black women. Black authors are relatively more present on topics related to farming studying, for example, studying *Bambara groundnut* in Agricultural sciences, *Cowpea Nodulation* and *Coca farming* in multidisciplinary research, *biosurfactants* in Engineering, *African agriculture* in Natural sciences, and *Farmers' social networks* in Social Sciences. Another set of topics where Black authors tend to publish more are related to the broader continental debates and regional migrant populations, such as *Nigerian Politics*, *Boko Haram terrorism*, and *Remittances*.

Figure 3. Proportion of papers from each topic by race and gender. Labels for the 10 topics with the highest proportion of each race & for women.

Colored authors publish relatively more articles on health-related topics, such as *COVID-19*. *Islam* and *Islam imaginaries* are the two topics from Humanities and Arts where Colored authors represent a larger proportion of authorships than the group's average. In the case of Indian/Asian women the topic of *Hindu diaspora* is particularly relevant. As was previously seen in Figure 2, Indian/Asian men publish more than average on topics from Engineering.

As a consistently large group across topics, White authors do not show a relative overrepresentation on any particular topic. Nevertheless, in Humanities and Arts, White women publish more about *Divorce mediation*, while White men publish on other Humanities topics such as *Calvinism* and Augustine's *Manichaean dilemma*. We can also observe variable field distribution of topics: White authors tend to have a lower representation on the majority of Social Sciences and Engineering topics, and more than average on Natural Science (for men), Humanities, and Health Sciences.

4. Discussion

Our results show a large underrepresentation of Black and Colored authors, and particularly of Black and Colored women. This underrepresentation is relative to the proportion of the national population from these same intersectional identities measured by the Census. This finding largely confirms the underrepresentation of marginalized populations in higher education: e.g., only 9.3% of Black Africans and Colored individuals aged over 25 years had a tertiary degree or higher, while this number rises to 21.1% for Indian/Asian and 39.8% for White individuals (Statistics South Africa, 2024). Therefore, future studies should examine other expected values, such as secondary or tertiary enrollment. Studying the degrees of underrepresentation at each stage in the academic pipeline will identify those places where

interventions are most necessary. We also observe a clear gendered pattern, demonstrating the peak of women's participation earlier in their careers (i.e., between 35-45), with a steeper attrition rate. This was also true for Black authors. This finding suggests policies are necessary to maintain the participation of women — and notably Black and Colored women — in science, particularly during times when they experience higher domestic responsibilities (Derrick et al., 2022). Domestic obligations can also lead to inequalities in international collaboration, where we find unequal representations of intersectional identities in terms of access to these international networks. Even more, with the pandemic lockdown, the domestic space became a congestive and more competitive place that reproduced gender inequalities for South African women academics (Walters et al., 2022).

Differential distributions across fields are also observed, by gender, race, and at the intersection of these variables. A lack of participation of a particular identity group in one area has strong implications for knowledge production (Kozłowski et al., 2022; Sugimoto et al., 2019). For example, the underrepresentation of women in Engineering may affect innovation, with consequences on the economy (Cook et al., 2021). We find further amplification of the relationship of identity and science at the level of topic, with homophily between the self-reported identity of the author and the topics with which they are disproportionately identities.

These results are relevant to understanding the harms of underrepresentation of diverse identities within science. The varying field and topic alignment compound with the underrepresentation generating knowledge gaps that reinforce inequalities in society. This highlights the need for active science policies to promote diversity among researchers. Of course, and especially in the case of South Africa, the roots of the underrepresentation go beyond science policy, as they are the result of the cumulative past and present structural inequalities. As a future line of work, we will study the different steps in which these unequal outcomes take place, from access to education to career promotion.

Open science practices

This project uses the SA Knowledgebase (SAK), hosted at the Centre for Research on Evaluation, Science and Technology (CREST) at Stellenbosch University. We decided to use this database which is not currently openly available because it is the only database that provides self-identification of authors' race and gender. Using an open bibliometric database would imply the automatic inference of race and gender based on authors names, which should be avoided if self-identification data exists.

Acknowledgments

The authors acknowledge the contributions of Herman Redelinghuys and Johann Mouton for their valuable support and comments.

Author contributions

Conceptualization: DK, TMW, VL, CRS

Methodology: DK, TMW, VL, CRS
Software: DK, CP
Validation: DN
Formal Analysis: DK, CP
Resources:
Data Curation: SL
Writing – Original Draft: DK
Writing – Review & Editing: DK, SL, CP, GMC, TMW, VL, DN, CRS
Visualization: DK
Supervision: VL, CRS
Project Administration: TMW, CRS
Funding Acquisition: TMW, CRS

Competing interests

The authors have no competing interests.

Funding information

This work was funded by the US National Science Foundation award 2152303.

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